

INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL LITERACY ON INFORMATION ENCOUNTERING AMONG RESEARCH STUDENTS IN SINDH, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This research is aimed to investigate the interconnection between digital literacy (DL) and information encountering among M.Phil and Ph.D (postgraduate) students enrolled in the faculty of social sciences and in the faculty of natural sciences in the University of Karachi and the University of Sindh Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan. A quantitative research method based on a survey questionnaire, was utilized to collect data from 278 students recruited through a convenient sampling technique. The collected data was analyzed using SPSS-23. The research depicted a high perceived DL and information encountering among the research participants. Moreover the results depicted that research students' DL was a positive correlative and significant predictor of their information encountering. The findings provided important insights to academicians, researchers, educational policy makers including the Higher Education Commission (HEC) for the value of DL for research students to use, share and manage unexpected information wisely.

INTRODUCTION

The inception of technology at large scale for information production, processing, storage and dissemination within widespread digital context require students to have competencies to control their learning. In view to this, digital literacy (DL) has evolved that enable students “to explore and face new technological situations in a flexible way, to analyze, select and critically evaluate data and information, to exploit technological potentials in order to represent and solve problems and build shared and collaborative knowledge, while fostering awareness of one’s own personal responsibilities and the respect of reciprocal rights/obligations” (Calvani, Fini, & Ranieri, 2009, pp. 60-61).

The previous literature has signified the worth of DL for students to take valuable advantage of digital trends (Oh et al., 2021) as it encompasses the sub-literacies including information literacy, computer literacy, media literacy, communication literacy, visual

literacy, artificial intelligence and technology literacy (Covello & Lei, 2010). Burton, Lawrence, Summers, Gibbings, and Noble (2013) argued that DL is demanded for students’ online learning. It facilitate students with necessary tool utilization for lifelong learning (Ala-Mutka, 2011). DL is imperative for individuals to use, understand, manage digital information and resources available in other complex media (Miranda, Isaias, & Pifano, 2018). Digital literate students have the ability to adopt with emerging technologies and tools to reach their desired goals (Ng, 2012). They are able to understand the facets and nature of information, evaluate information critically and apply information effectively and efficiently from multimedia formats (Hanik, 2020). DL involves digital reading and writing (Spires, Paul, & Kerkhoff, 2019), it enable students to acquire credible information resources, identify biased web contents, control digital information flow,

acquire knowledge and communicate it with others (Komlayut & Srivatanakul, 2017). DL is not merely the ability to use devices rather it includes cognitive, motor, sociological and emotional abilities required to surf digital context (Eshet-Alkalai, 2004). It empower individuals to perform optimum in society, these are the fundament skills, related to software (including AI,), hardware, operations related to online learning (Abbas, Hussain, & Rasool, 2019). It influence students' effective learning and classroom management (Muntu, Yuliana, & Tarigan, 2023). DL eliminate the harms associated with using these technologies such as data security (Berson & Berson, 2005). Students lacking digital literacy have futile learning efforts, their information search results often categorized as incredible and invalid (Qoidah, Zain, & Lawrenc, 2023). Despite the value and recognition for the positive role DL in students' academic, personal, and social life, relatively few reference exists evaluating DL among students (Abbas et al., 2019; Jan, 2018a, 2018b) excluding research students in Sindh, Pakistan. Hence, it elaborate the need for empirical assessment into the DL among research students in the province of Sindh, Pakistan.

Information Encountering

Searching and looking for a piece of information in an information rich context, much often resulted in an accidental discovery of unexpected information. This discovery of unexpected information engage individuals with some aim diverting activities. Unexpected discovery of information (information encountering) has become a phenomena while seeking information from online platforms. However, its management is a challenge which include saving, sharing, and effective future use. Erdelez (2005, pp. 179-180) defined information encountering as an "unexpected discovery of useful or interesting information... during the search for some other information." He further elaborate it as an "accidental discovery during an active search for some other information." Agarwal (2015, p. 12) also defined information encountering "as an incident-based, unexpected discovery of information leading to an aha! moment when a naturally alert actor is in a passive, no purposive state or in an active." Past researches have theorized the relationship between DL and information encountering such as Pálsdóttir

(2010) described that information encountering is feature of information seeking, hence it require individuals to have certain digital competencies to manage unexpectedly discovered information for later needs. Similarly, Ross (1999) stressed that information seeking assist in information encountering. Prior research somehow theorized the connection between DL (e.g., IL as type of literacy) and information encountering. However, no study has examined the connection between DL and information encountering empirically and directly. That warrants a research assessing interconnection between DL and information encountering.

Statement of the problem

Broadly describing, the assessment of digital literacy (DL) among varied population within academic domains have been undertaken in past. However, relatively few research exists measuring DL literacy among Pakistani students specifically among research students (Abbas et al., 2019; Ameen & Gorman, 2009; Irfan, Ali, & Sabir, 2022; Jan, 2018a). Likewise, a few studies evaluated the information encountering among learners (Awan, Ameen, & Soroya, 2019, 2021). Similarly, the connection between DL and information encountering has been well conceptualized and discussed in the available literature. Hence, no empirical study have appeared to examine the relationship between DL and information encountering. Therefore, there is a need to investigate the influence of DL on students' information encountering in academics. The assessment of DL, information encountering and the interconnection between the variables would offer a path to design and execute a need based DL into the curriculum. This research is intended to achieve following research objective (ROs):

RO1 - To investigate the perceived of digital literacy among research students

RO2 - To evaluate the perceived information encountering among research students

RO3 - To determine the influence of digital literacy on information encountering

Review of Literature and Hypothesis Development Digital Literacy

A plethora of research has shown the implication of digital literacy (DL) for students' school readiness, resilience and mental well-being Meng, Yan, Abbas, Shankar, and Subramanian (2023). Similarly, it demonstrated the assessment of DL among students such as Ali and Mughari (2025) revealed a high perceived DL among LIS students in Pakistan. Natural sciences' students had a high self-perceived DL (Holm, 2025). Contrary, Ndibalema (2025) in a systematic review of the literature exhibited that majority of the research assessing DL among students had reported inadequate DL among students in 21st century. Siregar, (2024) in a survey of the existing literature discovered that empowering students with DL posed a significant challenges of technological skills, access to modern technologies, lack DL integration into curriculum, inequality and teachers training. Aydınlar et al. (2024) concluded that female medical students had poor DL including the knowledge related to computer. Hussain (2023) surveyed the existing literature. The study reported a high DL among students. Moreover, the study reported that the students had understanding of smart use of technology for personal and academic use. Steinfeld (2023) found that the DL of currently enrolled graduate and postgraduate students has a significant and positive association with their misinformation behaviors among Israeli students. Muntu et al. (2023) in their research depicted that DL had a positive effect on classroom management and students learning effectiveness. Qoidah et al. (2023) revealed adequate DL among Indonesian and Gambian students. Moreover, their DL appeared to be a positive protector of learning outcomes. Visual impaired students possess a high level of DL in Turkey (Gül, 2022). Individuals exposed to DL have a great understanding to explore health related information using online platforms (Abdulai, Tiffere, Adam, & Kabanunye, 2021). Secondary school students in southern Punjab lack DL and they unaware of basic computer skills (Choudhary, Javed, & Khan, 2021). DL assignments resulted in a significant improvement among school students DL (Lazonder, Walraven, Gijlers, & Janssen, 2020). Davydov, Logunova, Maltseva, Sharikov, and Zadorin (2020) identify four distinct approaches to DL including ICT, industrial, media and information literacy, and psychological and pedagogical approaches. Moreover, empirically

the research found significant growth in media and DL since its emergence in 2010 in Russia. Anzak and Sultana (2020) women in ICT capital of Pakistan are equipped with DL which they use for managing affairs related to their daily life, social networks and looking for entrepreneurial opportunities. Abbas et al. (2019) found a connection between DL and students' research, communication skills, and confidence. Whereas, the DL appeared to be insignificant predictor of academic performance (e.g., CGPA). Perdana, Yani, Jumadi, and Rosana (2019) depicted that senior school students were deficient in DL skills including knowledge on hypertext, internet searching and content creation. Lack of technological infrastructure, availability of computing technology and infrequent trainings are barrier in students' DL. However, students had positive attitude and perception in learning digital literacy (Miranda et al., 2018). School students had a high perceived DL including mobile usage. However, these students lack technical skills such as installing software and preventing computer virus. Moreover, the study revealed no significance difference among male and female students regarding DL in Pakistan (Jan, 2018a). Jan (2018b) school students' DL effect their attitude towards information and communication technology use. Komlayut and Srivatanakul (2017) used a self-assessment method for DL among students. The study concluded ill visual-photo literacy and understanding of computer programs among students. Ng (2012) found adequate DL among undergraduate digital natives. Ameen and Gorman (2009) found ill provision in Pakistani academic institutions to implant DL among graduates. Despite the number of reference on DL, it is ascertained that DL among research students has attended less attention by researchers in Pakistan specifically in Sindh. Hence it merits an empirical investigation into the assessment of DL among research students in Sindh, Pakistan.

Information Encountering

The past research revealed the academicians' and researchers' interest concerning the evaluation of information encountering among individuals due to its positive association with daily life serendipitous information. For instance, Miwa et al. (2011) conducted interview of 11 undergraduate students.

The research reported that information encountering much often leads to temporarily deviation from foreground task which may be resulted in a change of destination. Jiang, Liu, and Chi (2015) identified fourteen factors that influence information encountering. These factors include actively diversity, curiosity, intentionality, attitudes, expertise, emotions, and sensitivity information users' related factors. Visibility, quality, relevance, and types information related factors. Interface usability and time limitations environmental related factors. Erdelez (2004) engaged conducted an experimental study using five factors of information encountering which include noticing, stopping, examining, capturing, and returning. The research reported that the majority of research participants were good at information noticing, and stayed on foreground problem while information encountering. Sun, Zhou, Wang, and Sharples (2022) found that individuals' positive emotion had a significant effect on serendipitous information encountering. Likewise, Jiang, Guo, Xu, and Fu (2019) found that visual stimulation excluding text contents trigger information encountering among students. Public libraries, digital settings such as web link structure and everyday life settings trigger the information encountering serendipity (Erdelez et al., 2016). Panahi, Watson, and Partridge (2016) found the six ways through social media influence the information encountering and tacit knowledge sharing. Such ways are described as (I) information publication and broadcasting, (II) dissemination of information, (III) filtered and personalized information feed, (IV) keeping up to dates, (V) documentation of experiences and knowledge, and (VI) retrievability. Awan et al. (2019) validated the suitability of Erdelez (2004) information encountering model among research students in Pakistani context. The research concluded the validity and suitability of the model. Moreover, the research reported that research students frequently using internet have high information encountering and sharing. Research students searching information for foreground experience less information encountering then those students who search internet for general information. Moreover, the research depicted that research students use simple tools in complex software to save encountered inform for future use (Awan et al., 2021).

The past research exhibited various information encountering models and individuals information encountering assessment with varied findings. Hence, limited reference were found investigating research students' information encountering experience. Therefore, the arguments light on the need for empirical investigation into research students information encountering.

Digital Literacy as predictor of academic variables

Prior research demonstrated a vital role of digital literacy (DL) on varied academic factors i.e., Ali and Mughari (2025) found a positive and significant relationship between LIS students' DL and academic performance in Pakistan. Puniatmaja, Parwati, Tegeh, and Sudatha (2024) exhibited that students' DL and their learning through electronic resources had a connection. Bender (2024) Associated DL with artificial intelligence literacy. Komarudin, Suherman, and Vidákovich (2024) reported that reading, mind mapping and sharing model, digital and mathematical literacy had a positive and significant interconnection among students. Nurharini, Hasan, Aziz, and Prasetyawan (2024) argued that the utilization of DL increase students' ability to use modern learning tools in academics. Younus et al. (2024) conducted a comparative analyses for DL. The study concluded that Pakistan should take solid steps to enhance DL among students, individuals and academicians to sustain digital development and technological endures. Surprisingly, technology acceptance model and digital literacy had no significant connection among engineering students in Pakistan (Mahnoor & Shazia Muheoddin, 2025). A research by (Holm, 2025) reported a high impact of students' DL on their academic achievement. Zhang and Hyland (2025) provided that students' DL had a positive influence on their engagement in automated writing evaluation. Parvez (2025) employed Pearson's r statistics for analysis and depicted a strong positive correlation between DL and cyber security vulnerability among Pakistani individuals. Yuan, Rehman, Altalbe, Rehman, and Shahiman (2024) in their study reached on the results that DL enhance students' academic self-efficacy and reduces procrastination. The research studies in past have justified the connection between DL and various academic phenomena. Similarly, the research somehow demonstrated the association

between DL and information encountering under the following heading:

Digital literacy and Information Encountering

Researchers in the literature on information and related activities proposed various model that elaborate individuals' information processes (Eisenberg & Berkowitz, 1990; Kuhlthau, 2002; McKenzie, 2000; Pappas & Tepe, 1997; Spitzer, Eisenberg, & Lowe, 1998). Erdelez, Basic, and Levitov (2011) found interconnection of these model with individuals' information encountering and proposed the inclusion of information encountering into these models. Stewart and Basic (2014) found that information literacy instructions help students in managing unexpected online information encountering. Information literacy empower them with skills to save the encountered information for later use in future. Purposeful information literacy training cultivate information encountering (Jiang et al., 2015). Erdelez et al. (2016) propose information literacy training to tackle information encountering. Information seeking assists information encountering (Ross, 1999). Erdelez (1995) information behavior and information encountering has a positive relationship. Individuals' information behavior trigger information encountering (Erdelez, 2004). A passive information seeking patterns leads to information encountering (Pálsdóttir, 2010). Information provided by authentic information sources including library and medical officers help students avoid information encountering (Seneviratne, Perera, & Seneviratne, 2015). Unintentional information search on internet leads to information encountering. Whereas, purposively information seeking helps to avoid and or save encountered information for later use (Awan et al., 2021). The past researchers conceptualized a direct or indirect relationship between information and DL and information encountering. Hence, it lacks an empirical study which merits an investigation into the interconnection between DL and information encountering. Based on the arguments emerged from the reviewed literature, this research postulated following hypothesis:

H1, *Digital literacy is positive and significant correlative and predictor of information encountering*

Research procedures and methods

Method

A quantitative survey research method was used to conduct the study. The survey research method is appropriate when a large and scattered research population.

Population, sample, sampling technique, data collection and analysis

The population of the current research is composed of M.Phil. and Ph.D. enrolled in the faculties of social sciences and natural sciences of University of Sindh Jamshoro and the University of Karachi. There were 74 departments in the both faculties of the selected universities (42 departments in University of Karachi and 32 departments in the University of Sindh Jamshoro).

The researchers estimated some 2220 total number of students pursuing their M.phil and Ph.D in the selected faculties of both universities. However, the sample of 327 research students was determined through Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table. The researchers approached the selected sample through a convenient sampling technique. The research participants were assured for their anonymity, confidentiality and the data usage solely for this research. However, the researchers distributed 5 research questionnaires in each department a total 370 questionnaires in the period of 6 months. Despite, the long period of time and researchers' consistent visit for data collection into the departments, the total of 278 completed usable responses could be received which were entered into SPSS v.25 for descriptive and inferential analysis.

Research instruments

The research questionnaire was consisted on a total of 44 items. 29 items were related to digital literacy, 11 items of information encountering and 4 items related to participants' demographic profile. The description of instruments used is presented under the following headings:

Digital literacy

Variety of instruments exists in the available literature. Hence, the researchers adopt Digital

Literacy as Whole of Digital Competences scale developed by Bayrakci and Narmanlioğlu (2021). This measure was adopted due to its' ability to assess DL comprehensively. The scale consisted of 29 items in total. All the items were measured on a five points Likert scale such as 1 equal to strongly disagree and 5 equal to strongly agree.

Information encountering

The 11 items related to information encountering were adopted from the study entitled as individuals' difference in opportunistic discovery of information by Wise, Erdelez, and Chiang (2012). The items were adopted because most of the researchers investigating information encountering had utilized this scale as it reported to be most comprehensive, reliable and valid research scale. The items pertaining to information encountering were also measured on a five points Likert scale i.e., 1 equal to strongly disagree and 5 equal to strongly agree.

Reliability and validity of the research instruments

The reliability and validity of the scales were ensured through factor loadings, Cronbach's alpha (*a*) and composite reliability (CR). The recommended value of factor loadings should be greater than 0.3 (Garson, 2013), whereas, the values for *a* and CR above 0.5 is recommended (Hair, Risher, Sarstedt, & Ringle, 2019). The factor loadings of scales was between 400 to 767 and 450 to 831. It revealed that items of both scales i.e., digital literacy and information encountering are loaded under their latent variables in Table 2 and 3. Likewise, *a* value for 29 items of digital literacy was *a* = .867 and for information encountering 11 items was *a* = .777. The composite reliability of digital literacy was CR = 945, and

information encountering was CR = 895. Exhibited that both scales hold reliability.

The validity consisted on convergent validity and discriminant validity was evaluated with average variance extracted (AVE) as researchers demonstrated the AVE as main statistical test to determine whether an instrument is valid. The cut off value for AVE is close to 4 or greater. AVE for digital literacy was 396 whereas, the AVE of information encountering was observed as AVE = 486. Demonstrated that both scales had convergent validity. However, the discriminant validity was assessed using Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion who proposed the square root ($\sqrt{}$) of AVE should be greater than the observed value of correlation among the variables. The observed score for the square root of AVE for digital literacy was $\sqrt{} = 0.629$, and for digital literacy was $\sqrt{} = 0.691$ greater than the observed correlation 570**. Hence, it is concluded that the reliability and validity of the scales is determined. (See Table 4)

Results

Demographics of the research participants

Table 1 shows that 138 (49.6%) male and 140 (50.4%) female research students participated in the research. their age related response shows that 113 (40.6%) a large number of research respondents were between the age bracket of 20-25 followed by 108 (38.8%) 26-30, 50 (18.0%) between 31-35 and only 7 (2.5%) respondents were 36 and above. Of 278, 213 (76.6%) students were pursuing their M.phil and 65 (23.4%) were enrolled in Ph.D degree program. The discipline wise distribution exhibits that 167 (60.1%) students participated from behavioral and social sciences and 111 (39.9%) participated from natural sciences.

Table 1
Demographics n=278

Characteristics	Categories	Frequencies	Percentage
Gender	Male	138	49.6
	Female	140	50.4
Age	20-25	113	40.6
	26-30	108	38.8
	31-35	50	18.0
	36 and above	7	2.5
Program of study	M.phil	213	76.6

Discipline	Ph.D	65	23.4
	Behavioral and social sciences	167	60.1
	Natural sciences	111	39.9

Descriptive statistics

RO1 - To evaluate perceived of digital literacy among research students

The research participants were asked to respond their perceived digital literacy on 29 statements carrying a five points Likert scale such as 1 = strongly disagree; 2 = disagree; 3 = I am uncertain; 4 = agree; 5 = strongly agree. Table 2 presents the descriptive analysis (mean and standard deviation) for perceived digital literacy. The results revealed that these selected participants were either agree or strongly agree with statements

which revealed adequate digital literacy among these research students as they can install/ format the operating systems (M = 3.95, SD. = 1.070), know about hardware and software technologies (M = 3.95, SD. = 1.181), how to behave to others' and protect data online (M = 3.87, SD. = .995), add a web page in bookmark (M = 3.46, SD. = 1.163) and know how to restricts apps' to access personal information including contacts, location, camera etc. (M = 3.39, SD. = .990).

Table 2
Perceived digital literacy

S#	Statements	Mean	Standard deviation	Factor Loadings
1	I know how to restrict apps' access to my personal information (location, contacts, camera, etc.)	3.39	.990	0.742
2	I can add a web page that I use to bookmarks or favorites.	3.46	1.163	0.767
3	I can effectively use at least one software related to my field (Photoshop, SPSS, Premiere, Office Word, etc.).	3.47	1.280	0.639
4	I can use at least one programming language (Java, C, Visual Basic, PHP, etc.).	3.50	1.098	0.654
5	With the help of digital technologies, I can change various images (photography, sound recording and video, etc.) and produce new content.	3.53	1.213	0.452
6	I can change the privacy / security settings on my social media posts and profile.	3.53	1.089	0.680
7	I can use the calendar on mobile devices not only just for looking at date but also as reminder, for taking notes and creating events.	3.61	.961	0.618
8	I can do activities such as "uploading videos / broadcasting" online.	3.63	1.010	0.400
9	I can change the proxy /dns settings of devices to access banned websites.	3.64	1.018	0.601
10	I can recognize and block unwanted / spam emails and phishing messages.	3.64	1.011	0.590
11	I can write and share on my own blog page or on different blogs	3.66	1.105	0.462
12	I know the concepts such as licensed software, demo software, pirated software, malware, crack etc	3.67	1.016	0.509

13	I can develop software / applications based on digital technologies.	3.69	1.016	0.504
14	I can use cloud computing technologies (Google Drive, I cloud, Dropbox, etc.) effectively in daily life	3.70	1.009	0.657
15	I can design and publish a website using web design systems (Weebly, WordPress, etc.)	3.71	.975	0.675
16	I can recognize digital games and content that are suitable for cognitive and moral development.	3.71	1.031	0.585
17	I am aware of the ethical and legal responsibilities that may arise from copyright violations in digital environments.	3.73	1.087	0.748
18	I can use digital technologies effectively in daily practice such as reservation, shopping, address finding etc.	3.74	1.065	0.695
19	I can effectively use e-Government applications (MHRS, UYAP, tax & penalty inquiry etc.)	3.76	.996	0.443
20	I am aware that everything I do online is recorded.	3.76	1.036	0.595
21	I know how to create a strong password	3.80	.940	0.693
22	I can install software or programs on my computer or other electronic devices	3.82	1.075	0.660
23	I know what Torrent, Internet, World Wide Web (WWW) terms mean.	3.85	.958	0.507
24	I know how to behave to protect others' and own personal data (photo, address, family information, etc.) online	3.87	.995	0.736
25	I am aware of the ethical and legal responsibilities such as cyberbullying (insult, swearing, hate speech, etc.) and online abusing	3.87	1.125	0.762
26	I can inquire from different sources whether the information I accessed online is correct or not.	3.88	.938	0.715
27	I am aware that my personal or legal rights (privacy, copyright, freedom of speech, etc.) Continue in digital media as well as in daily life.	3.89	.991	0.658
28	I know what hardware and software technologies mean.	3.95	1.181	0.742
29	I can install / format the operating system on my computer	3.95	1.070	0.767

Note: items adopted from BAYRAKCI and NARMANLIOĞLU (2021), scale : 1 = strongly disagree; 2 = disagree; 3 = I am uncertain; 4 = agree; 5 = strongly agree. Bold value in the last column of the table refers to factor loadings of items.

RO2 - To evaluate perceived information encountering among research students

The perceived information encountering was assessed using 11 items on a five point likert scale i.e., 1 = strongly disagree; 2 = disagree; 3 = I am uncertain; 4 = agree; 5 = strongly agree in Table 3. The results shows that participants were agreed on statements that they encounter unexpected information when they browse

the web they notice information they were not looking for (M = 3.81, SD. = .924), find unexpected information online that is interesting, they search for more information on that topic (M = 3.81, SD. = 1.142), When searching for information online, they scan things that are not related to what they are

looking for (M = 3.80, SD. = 1.225), When they find unexpected information online that is interesting, they open a new browser tab or a new window to explore the information further (M = 3.59, SD. =

1.179) and they e-mail links to interesting webpages to family members, friends or colleagues (M = 3.42, SD. = 1.411).

Table 3
Perceived information encountering

S#	Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Factor loadings
1	When I browse the web, I notice information I was not looking for	3.81	.924	0.652
2	When I find unexpected information online that is interesting, I search for more information on that topic	3.81	1.142	0.835
3	When searching for information online, I scan things that are not related to what I'm looking for	3.80	1.225	0.685
4	When I notice information that I was not looking for online, I tend to interrupt my original search	3.79	1.125	0.598
5	If something unexpected catches my interest, when surfing the web, I bookmark it with my web browser	3.79	1.102	0.450
6	After keeping my own relevant information or sharing it with others return to my original goal	3.77	1.054	0.707
7	I get interrupted when stop to look at something unrelated from my assigned goal	3.67	1.173	0.667
9	When searching for information online, I come across other information that I was not looking for	3.66	.999	0.559
10	When I find unexpected information online that is interesting, I open a new browser tab or a new window to explore the information further	3.59	1.179	0.760
11	I e-mail links to interesting webpages to family members, friends or colleagues	3.42	1.411	0.831

Note: items adopted from Wise et al. (2012), scale : 1 = strongly disagree; 2 = disagree; 3 = I am uncertain; 4 = agree; 5 = strongly agree. Bold value in the last column of the table refers to factor loadings of items.

RO3 - To determine the influence of digital literacy on information encountering

Hypothesis Assessment: H1, *Digital literacy is positive significant correlative and predictor of information encountering*

The researchers used Pearson's Product Moment (Pearson's r) to assess the relationship between digital literacy and information encountering. The performed test for correlation depicted a positive and significant correlation between digital literacy and information encountering ($r = .570^{**}$). The power of correlated was assessed through Cohen (1988) proposed criteria. The criterion connotes $r < .10$ to

weak, $r < .30$ moderate and $r < .50$ strong correlation. The observed value of correlation between the variables was $r = .570$ mean there was a strong correlation between digital literacy and information encountering in Table 4. Likewise, the effect of digital literacy (predicting variable) on information encountering (response variable) was evaluated using simple linier regression model. The model observed Beta = .807, F = 136.821 with $p > .001$ revealed a positive and significant effect of digital literacy on information encountering. The value of R^2 was .576

which mean that digital literacy explain 57.6% the information encountering. Hence, the hypothesis H1 accepted based on the results as digital literacy

appeared to be a positive correlative and predictor of information encountering. (See Table 4)

Table 4

Information literacy is positive significant correlative and predictor of information encountering

Hypothesis	Correlation	DL	DV	IE	DV	AVE	CR	Remarks
H1	Digital Literacy	1	$\sqrt{}$	=		396	945	Accepted
			0.629					
	Information encountering (DL)	570**		1	$\sqrt{}$	= 0.486	0.895	
					0.691			
Regression		Beta	R ²		F	Sig		
Digital literacy predicts information encountering (IE)		.807	.576		136.821	.000		

Note: ** correlation significant at the level of 0.01 (two-tailed) off-diagonal elements DV are discriminant validity, AVE = average variance extracted, CR = composite reliability.

Discussion

The descriptive statistics indicated that the research students perceived themselves as digitally literate as the agreed with statements related to their digital literacy. These results are quite surprising as Asad, Gul, and Lashari (2020) stressed that Pakistani educational system lack technology related policies and practices. Likewise, other researchers also found ill provision for information and digital literacy instructions in Pakistani universities (Naveed & Mahmood, 2022; Naveed & Saadia, 2023; Saadia & Naveed, 2023). However, the question that how these research students had developed digital literacy may be worth interesting to explore in future studies. Perhaps, these students overestimated their digital literacy of they may have learned these skills by themselves by participating in research related workshops or from their course which most often consist of technology related tasks such as information and research management software. However, these findings are supported by Hussain (2023); Qoidah et al. (2023) who found adequate digital literacy among students. These findings are also align with the findings of Ng (2012) who reported high digital literacy among undergraduate digital natives.

The results indicated that research students’ perceived information encountering was also high as they encounter unexpected information while surfing online information mediums including internet and web resources. Undoubtedly, digital literacy encompasses ethnic and responsibility, knowledge and functional skills, daily usage, advance protection, privacy and security and social dissemination skills which practicing individuals can gently handle the encountered information such as they can open a new window to explore further relevant information on a topic, return to own foreground needed information, bookmark the encountered information for future use or share it with others via email and other platforms to those who may find unexpected information useful. These findings are endorsed the findings of Awan et al. (2019) who depicted that research students who use internet and online media frequently have high information encountering and sharing. However, these findings disagreed with the findings of Awan et al. (2021) who reported that the research students while searching information related to foreground experience less information encountering. The hypothesis assessment exhibited that research students’ digital literacy was positive significant correlative and predictor of their information encountering (H1). Empirically the interconnection

between digital literacy and information encountering have been investigated for the first time. Hence, these findings required to be corroborated with future research investigations. However, the existing literature somehow supports the findings such as Awan et al. (2021) who depicted that Pakistani research students use digital software tools to save and share unexpected or accidentally acquired information for future need. Erdelez et al. (2011) also found that various information literacy related models have provision to handle the encountered information. Information literacy instructions enable students to manage unexpected online information encountering (Stewart & Basic, 2014). Erdelez et al. (2016) proposed information literacy training to equip students with information encountering skills. Information seeking assists information encountering (Ross, 1999). Seneviratne et al. (2015) asserted that information provided by professionals such as librarians and medical officer help students to avoid information encountering. Pálsdóttir (2010) also found a connection between information seeking and information encountering.

Conclusions

Based on the empirical findings this study concludes that research students perceived digital literacy is high. However, the factors behind the perceived high digital literacy are still unclear. In case if these students overestimated their digital literacy than the concerned stakeholders should initiate measures as most of the research proposed that overestimation of such skills may lead them to a resistant behavior for further information literacy learning (Mughari, Naveed, & Rafique, 2023). Likewise, the students' information encountering and management was also high which are supported by their digital literacy practices. Moreover, the research depicted that research students' digital literacy appeared to be positive, significant correlative and predictor of their information encountering.

Research implications

The research in hand has some theoretical and practical implications. Such as the theoretical implications include: firstly the investigation of perceived digital literacy and information encountering among research students of Sindh as no

such study was conducted before. Secondly the novelty of the research as not study in past appeared to examine the interconnection between digital literacy and information encountering. The practical implications include: firstly, the research findings provided an insight into the empirical evidence for the usefulness of digital literacy to foster research students information encountering therefore, the academicians, researchers and other educational stockholders should consider the design, developments and integration of a need based digital literacy instruction program. Moreover, a collective efforts of information professional and teaching faculty may require to effectively execute the digital literacy program.

Limitations and Directions

This research offer a self-assessment opportunity to research students to rank their digital literacy and information encountering. Hence, the researchers criticize the method as the research participants may underestimate or overestimate their perceived phenomena. However, this may be deemed as a potential limitation associated with the research. Moreover, the research participants were recruited through a convenient sampling technique. Therefore, the generalizability of this research may be considered as the participants may not represent all the research students from other disciplines such as law, engineering etc. The future researches investigation should consider the potentials limitations of this study and conduct the same study by expanding its scope which include research students from all over Pakistan or adding other variables such as connection of digital literacy with students' academic engagement, online learning, entrepreneurship, creativity, innovation, and so on.

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